

Comparative Study on the Impact of Internal Control of Listed Companies on Earnings Management between Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchange in China

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Abstract

Taking 884 Manufacturing Listed Companies in Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchange in 2017 as samples, this paper empirically examines the relationship between internal control and earnings management of the two stock exchanges. The final conclusion confirms that, there is a significant negative correlation between internal control and earnings management of manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchanges. Compared with the relationship between internal control (IC) and earnings management (EM) of manufacturing listed companies in Shanghai Stock Exchange and that of Shenzhen Stock Exchange, the negative correlation between internal control and earnings management is more prominent in Shenzhen Stock Exchange which includes 70% manufacturing listed companies. Shenzhen Stock Exchange includes not only main board market, but also small and medium-sized enterprise board (SMEB) and Growth Enterprise Market (GEM). It indicates that, IC regulation enforced in main board listed company has made a good effect in manufacturing industry. The improvement of internal control quality can better regulate earnings management behavior of listed manufacturing companies. Here suggests that, IC regulation can be enforced in SMEB and GEM in right chance, which is helpful to the healthy and orderly development of manufacturing industry in China.

Keywords: Earnings Management; Internal Control; Comparative Study; Manufacturing Listed Companies

1.0 Introduction

Due to the universality, legitimacy, secrecy and the non-reality of removing earnings management (EM) (Yang Shunhua, 2010) ^[1], corporate earnings management activities have been a hot topic for scholars at home and abroad. With the continuous improvement of China's capital marketization, the diversification of the operating scope of listed companies and the complication of financial conditions, it is very common that managers often engage in earnings management considering their own interests and business operating. The question that arises is, what factors can effectively regulate the company's earnings management behavior? Under the modern management model, internal control is an important part of the corporate governance structure. As a management mechanism, internal control is highly valued by enterprises. Since the Enron incident, the United States issued the SOX requiring listed companies to strengthen internal control construction. China's Ministry of Finance and the Securities Regulatory Commission and other departments issued the "Basic Standards for Enterprise Internal Control" and "Supporting Guidelines for Enterprise Internal Control" in 2008 and 2010, respectively. China's Shenzhen and Shanghai main board listed companies are required to implement these standards in batches from 2011 and 2012. Through empirical research on the relationship between internal control and earnings management, many scholars found that, effective internal control can indeed regulate corporate earnings management behavior (Fang Hongxing et al., 2011) ^[2] (Hu Quying et al., 2016) ^[3] (Li Ying et al. 2016) ^[4]. The Shanghai stock exchange constitutes main board (MB) market, whereas the Shenzhen stock exchange includes main board, small and medium-sized enterprise board (SMEB) and Growth Enterprise Market (GEM). The internal control normative guidelines only are required enforcement in the main board market; therefore, Shenzhen SME Board and GEM have not enforced the internal control normative guidelines. What then, is the difference of the relationship between the internal control and earnings management of manufacturing listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchange?

In view of the above issues, for the research sample, an empirical research is conducted on manufacturing listed companies which are enforced internal control guidelines (ICG) and related to national economy and people's livelihood on Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchange in 2017. First, the relationships between internal control and earnings management of all manufacturing listed companies are studied; and then the degree of earnings management of Shenzhen and Shanghai listed companies and their internal control effects on earnings management are compared, and finally, the implementation effect of ICG is analyzed. The main contributions of this article are:

From the sample selection, this article selects all the manufacturing companies listed on Shenzhen stock exchange, including main board, the SME board, the Growth Enterprise Market and Shanghai stock exchange as the research sample and fill the limitations of the previous research which only focus on the main board research. The sample selection covers a wider scope which supports the conclusion, enriches and expands the research field of earnings management.

In terms of content, not only all manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen Stock Exchange was compared with that of Shanghai stock exchange, but also considering the differences of listed companies between different stock exchanges, this paper studied and compared the correlation between the internal control(IC) and earnings management(EM) of the listed companies in Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges, as well as the correlation between IC and EM in listed companies in the manufacturing industry between Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges, which one is more significant, and verifies the implementation effect of the internal control normative guidelines in the main board market.

2.0 Theoretical Analysis and Research Assumptions

2.1 Principal Agent Theory

The principal-agent theory holds that the distinguishing feature of the modern enterprise system is that the management right is separated from the ownership. The owner entrusts professional managers to manage the company. The company's value and manager's salary are often linked to the company's operating performance. However, the principal-agent relationship in which ownership and management rights are separated must be out of balance, so the principal and agent have inconsistent goals. The client seeks to maximize the value of the company and the interests of shareholders, while the agent hopes to use the least working time and obtain the maximum reward. The different goals between the two can easily lead to conflicts of interest. When the agent's interests are linked to the company's earnings, the agents will have earnings management motivations for their own consideration. They may use professional knowledge and judgment to adjust the earnings to meet predetermined earnings expectations.

2.2 Theory of Information Asymmetry

The theory of information asymmetry holds that in the case of information asymmetry, the owner, as an outsider, lacks a sufficient and effective source of information and cannot check whether the manager has fulfilled the contract fully. As an insider manager, he has real accounting information. In the absence of effective supervision, managers are more likely to perform earnings management for performance and self-interest, such as choosing accounting policies and methods that maximize their own interests to achieve earnings goals.

2.3 Theory of Signal Transmission

According to the theory of signal transmission, in order to pass on the good information of business conditions to investors, creditors, the public, and government regulators, it is very likely that company managers will use their information advantages and professional skills to conduct earnings management.

Manufacturing listed companies are the backbone of the entire capital market and are the pillar industries related to the growth of the national economy in China. It involves all aspects of the national economy and

directly or indirectly affects the development of other industries. The capital flows involved purchasing, production, and sales process, as well as the confirmation and measurement of costs, expenses, and income in the manufacturing industry are all areas where managers can easily manage earnings. Therefore, this article selects manufacturing companies as research samples which are more representative.

One of the fundamental objectives of internal control is to guarantee the quality of financial reports, hence theoretically internal control can regulate earnings management behavior and improve the quality of accounting information of enterprises. Overall, effective internal control, as an internal governance mechanism, can regulate earnings management from two paths: Firstly, controlling and monitoring activities can discourage management and other employees from deliberately misjudging the opportunity and motivation to increase earnings, and can increase their implementation costs (Zhang You tang, 2017) ^[5]. Secondly, good internal controls can prevent unintentional, random, procedural earnings errors in the information transmission process (Zhang Guoqing, 2008) ^[6]. After China's internal control normative guidelines are enforced in the main board market, the higher the quality of internal control, the stronger the company's motivation for disclosure, and the better it can regulate earnings management. Integrating the above analysis, the following assumptions are made:

Hypothesis 1: The quality of internal control of manufacturing listed companies is negatively correlated with the degree of earnings management.

Chinese companies mainly choose to be listed on Shenzhen stock exchange and Shanghai stock exchange. Shanghai stock exchange is the main board market whereas Shenzhen stock exchange includes main board market, small and medium-sized boards (SEMB) and Growth Enterprise Market (GEM). The main board market is mainly large-volume enterprises with sufficient capital, but SEMB and GEM are mostly small and medium-sized enterprises and innovative and entrepreneurial private enterprises. The "Basic Standards for Enterprise Internal Control" and "Supporting Guidelines for Enterprise Internal Control" issued by the Ministry of Finance in conjunction with the Securities Regulatory Commission and other departments only require mandatory implementation by listed companies in main board of Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchange, that is, the current mandatory guidelines for internal control do not include listed companies in SMEB and GEM . Compared to the main board, the internal control quality of SMEB and GEM is relatively low, and the information disclosure is not standardized. In addition, the companies listed on the SMEB and GEM are small, have weak market competitiveness with few sources of funds. In order to attract more investors and maintain their market position, these listed companies have strong motivation of earnings management because of less internal control compared to the main board market. Based on the above analysis, the following assumptions is derived:

Hypothesis 2: Compared with manufacturing listed companies in Shanghai stock exchange, manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen stock exchange have a more significant negative correlation between internal control quality and earnings management.

3.0 Sample Selection and Study Design

3.1 Sample Selection and Data Source

The financial data used in this research comes from Guotaian CSMAR database, WIND financial database and annual financial reports of listed companies. The internal control index is taken from the internal control database of Dibo Risk Management Company. The research samples of this article come from all A-share manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchange in 2017. On the basis of the original data, and in order to avoid the influence of extreme values, combined with the actual needs of data processing, companies with less than three consecutive years of data, missing data, and ST in the samples, are excluded and finally this paper can sort out 884 listed manufacturing companies as research samples. The 884 listed manufacturing companies are made up of 576 from Shenzhen stock exchange and 308 from Shanghai stock exchange.

3.2 Variable design

3.2.1 Independent Variable

In 2010, China set up a research group specifically to quantify the internal control of companies based on China's national conditions and the internal control of capital market, and constructed a set of scientific, persuasive Dibo DIB listed companies internal control index that are suitable for China's national conditions. The internal control index has authority and social recognition. This article uses Dibo's 2017 listed company's internal control index to quantify the quality of internal control. The internal control index is divided by 100 for measurement and is recorded as IC.

3.2.2 Dependent Variable

There are many models for measuring earnings management. This article chooses amended JONES Model by measuring Accrual earnings management, this model is widely used, for good effect. The calculation method of the model is as follows: First, calculate the total accrued profit TA according to formula (1); TA Substituting formula (2) to calculate the coefficient value; then substituting the coefficient value into formula (3) to obtain the non-manipulability accrued profit(NDA); Finally Substituting NDA into the formula (4) to obtain the controllable accrued profit(DA).

$$TA_{i,t} = NP_{i,t} - CFO_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{TA_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = \alpha_1 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_2 \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_3 \frac{PPE_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

$$NDA_{i,t} = \alpha_1 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_2 \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t} - \Delta REC_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_3 \frac{PPE_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} \quad (3)$$

$$DA_{i,t} = \frac{TA_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} - NDA_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

Where: i is company i ; t is t period; $TA_{i,t}$ for total accrued profits; $NP_{i,t}$ for net profit; $CFO_{i,t}$ net cash flow from operating activities; $A_{i,t-1}$ for total assets. $\Delta REV_{i,t}$ is the difference between the main business income of period t and $t-1$; $\Delta REC_{i,t}$ is the difference of accounts receivable between period t and $t-1$; $PPE_{i,t}$ is the total fixed assets; $NDA_{i,t}$ is the non-manipulability accrued profit; $DA_{i,t}$ is manipulated accruals.

This article studies the degree of corporate earnings management. An enterprise may increase or decrease earnings, but whether it's up or down, in the case of the same value, the degree of earnings management is the same. Therefore, this article chooses the absolute value of the controllable accrued profit $|DA|$ to indicate the degree of earnings management, which can be avoided $DA_{i,t}$ the positive and negative to offset and make the measurement result more accurate. $|DA|$ larger value indicates a greater degree of earnings management.

3.2.3 Control Variable

In order to study other control factors affecting earnings management reference to existing research by other scholars (Fang Hongxing et al., 2011, Hu Quying et al., 2016, Li Ying et al. 2016). This article selects company size (SIZE), asset-liability ratio (LEV), sales revenue growth rate (GROWTH), Return on total asset (ROA), and equity concentration (TOP10) are used as control variables. The definitions of each variable are shown in Table 1:

Table 1 Definition of all Variables Summary Table

Variable Type	Name	Code	Calculation Method
Dependent variable	Earnings management	DA	Modified the JONES model to calculate the controllable accrued profit (DA), take the absolute value
Independent variable	Internal Control Quality	IC	Dibo Listed Company Internal Control Index / 100
Control variable	Company Size	SIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets at the end of the year
	Asset and liability ratio	LEV	Total Liabilities / Total Assets
	Revenue growth rate	GROWTH	(Sales revenue for the current year sales revenue for the previous year) / sales revenue for the previous year
	Return on total assets	ROA	Net profit / average balance of assets
	Equity concentration	TOP10	Shareholdings of the top ten shareholders

3.3 Model Design

In order to explore the impact degree of internal control of manufacturing listed companies on earnings management, a multiple regression model is constructed to test the above theoretical assumptions proposed:

$$|DA| = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IC + \beta_2 SIZE + \beta_3 LEV + \beta_4 GROWTH + \beta_5 ROA + \beta_6 TOP10 + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

In the above model, | DA | is the absolute value of controllable accrued profits, IC is the internal control index of Dibo listed companies divided by 100, SIZE is the size of the company, LEV is the asset structure indicator asset-liability ratio, GROWTH is the growth ability indicator sales revenue growth rate, and ROA is profitability indicator total assets return rate, TOP10 is equity concentration

4. Empirical Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Code	Sample Size	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Average Value	Standard Deviation
DA	884	0.000033	0.085806	0.033189	0.021167
IC	884	2.8032	8.4803	6.5158	0.7192
SIZE	884	19.5350	27.3074	22.3599	1.1484
LEV	884	0.0120	1.0586	0.3994	0.1820
GROWTH	884	-0.8625	58.4869	0.3985	2.2832
ROA	884	-0.2174	0.3610	0.0467	0.0542
TOP10	884	0.1490	0.9433	0.5644	0.1410

Descriptive statistics of the model are shown in table 2 above. It can be seen from the statistical results that, earnings management| DA | average value is 0.033189, the maximum and minimum values are 0.085806 and 0.000033 respectively, and the difference between them are much more. It shows that the degree of earnings management of each company is different, which indicates that the degree of earnings management among main board, SMEB and GEM is quite different. But from Standard deviation of 0.021167, the degree of discreteness of earnings management is not so large, indicating that the enterprise's earnings management is relatively concentrated and there is little difference. The maximum internal control quality IC is 8.4803 and the minimum is 2.8032, which indicates that the level of internal control of listed manufacturing companies in China is uneven and the quality is different. It indicates that the internal control in Main board are much better than SMEB and GEM board. Standard deviation 0.7192 is high which prove the above situation. China's manufacturing listed enterprises in SMEB and GEM should strengthen the internal control construction to regulate the level of earnings management. However, the high IC average of 6.5158 indicates that the overall

internal control quality of China's manufacturing listed enterprises is constantly improving, which indicates that the manufacturing listed companies in main board are getting better in implementing the national internal control guidelines, and the state government and enterprises are paying more attention to internal control construction. The standard deviations of the company size and sales revenue growth rate are relatively large, which indicate that these indicators have a large degree of dispersion, and the companies operating development status are significantly different. The standard deviations of the asset-liability ratio, the return on total assets and the equity concentration are relatively small, which indicates that the manufacturing enterprise's overall production and operation risks are relatively low, the profitability is not so different, and the equity is relatively concentrated.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

From the correlation coefficient between the variables (see Table 3), it can be seen that the correlation coefficient of internal control quality (IC) is -0.154, which is significantly negative at the level of 1%, indicating that the quality of internal control and earnings management are significantly negative correlation, indicating that the better the internal control quality of an enterprise, the lower the degree of earnings management. Earnings management is significantly positively related to the growth rate of sales revenue and the asset-liability ratio, indicating that the higher the two rates, the easier it is to trigger management's earnings management motivation in order to meet the debt contract and expected earnings. There is a negative correlation between earnings management and the size of the company, earnings management and the return on total assets, but the impact is not significant.

Table 3 Pearson correlation analysis

	DA	IC	SIZE	LEV	GROWTH	ROA	TOP10
DA	1						
IC	-0.154 ***	1					
SIZE	-0.036	0.219 ***	1				
LEV	0.044 *	-0.006	0.520 ***	1			
GROWTH	0.081 ***	-0.078 ***	0.000	0.093 ***	1		
ROA	-0.025	0.297 ***	0.074	-0.272 ***	0.014	1	
TOP10	0.043 *	-0.047 *	-0.123 ***	-0.106 ***	0.017	0.039	1

Note: *** significant at 1% level; ** significant at 5% level; * significant at 10% level

4.3 Multiple Collinearity Analysis

Based on statistical principles, this paper conducted a multicollinearity analysis on the independent and control variables before performing the regression analysis to test whether the autocorrelation between the variables would affect the empirical results. According to the results of collinearity test shown in Table 4 below, the tolerances of all variables are greater than 0.6, and the VIF is less than 2, indicating that all variables do not have multiple collinearity problems with each other, so regression analysis can be performed.

Table 4 Collinearity test results

Model	Collinear statistics Tolerance	VIF
IC	0.864	1.157
SIZE	0.648	1.543
LEV	0.622	1.608
GROWTH	0.977	1.023
ROA	0.800	1.250
TOP10	0.980	1.021
IC	0.864	1.157

4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

4.4.1 Full Sample Regression Analysis

A multiple regression model is established to verify the correlation between internal control and earnings management of listed companies in China's manufacturing industry. The full sample regression analysis results are shown in Table 5 below:

Table 5 Results of Regression Analysis of the full Sample Model

Variables Code	Non-Normalized Coefficient		Standard Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Standard Error	Trial Version		
(constant)	0.071	0.016		4.303	0.000
IC	-0.004	0.001	-0.15	-4.199	0.000
SIZE	-0.001	0.001	-0.04	-0.967	0.334
LEV	0.009	0.005	0.073	1.741	0.082
GROWTH	0.001	0.000	0.061	1.816	0.07
ROA	0.016	0.015	0.041	1.093	0.275
TOP10	0.005	0.005	0.036	1.075	0.283
F value	31.44				
P value	0.000				
after adjustment R ²	0.0795				

From table 5 it can be seen that the R square after regression adjustment is 0.0795, indicating that the established regression model can explain the earnings management (dependent variable) change of 7.95%. The degree of fitting is not particularly good, but according to the relevant econometric theory, degree of fitting is allowed to be low when the sample size is large enough, and it can be known from the significance of test result of the multiple regression equation, $F = 31.44$ with a corresponding p-value 0.000, less than significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, showing the regression equation is overall significant. -0.004 is the correlation coefficient between internal control and earnings management, which indicates that effective internal control can regulate earnings management and confirm hypothesis 1. From this, the linear regression equation of the multiple regression model can be obtained:

$$|DA| = 0.071 - 0.004 * IC - 0.001 * SIZE + 0.009 * LEV + 0.001 * GROWTH + 0.016 * ROA + 0.005 * TOP10$$

4.4.2 Comparative Analysis of Sample Regression between Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchange

China's Shenzhen stock exchange includes the main board, SMEB and GEM. The Shanghai stock exchange is mainly the main board market. Mostly listed companies with a relatively good management foundation and a relatively large asset scale are in the main board, private enterprises are mainly in SMEB and GEM. Different stock exchanges contain different sections, which have different requirements for listed company's supervision and internal control disclosure. Taking into account the differences of different stock exchanges, further regression analysis is performed. The results of the regression analysis are shown in Tables 6 and 7 below.

Table 6 Regression Analysis Results of Manufacturing listed Companies in Shenzhen Stock Exchange

Code	Non-Normalized Coefficient		Standard Coefficient	t	Sig.	Collinear Statistics	
	B	Standard error	trial version			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	0.07	0.023		3.034	0.003		
IC	-0.005	0.001	-0.153	-3.439	0.001	0.855	1.17
SIZE	-0.001	0.001	-0.027	-0.542	0.588	0.674	1.484
LEV	0.004	0.006	0.034	0.665	0.506	0.642	1.557
GROWTH	0.001	0.000	0.076	1.799	0.073	0.946	1.057

ROA	0.022	0.018	0.056	1.215	0.225	0.8	1.25
TOP10	0.01	0.007	0.061	1.45	0.148	0.966	1.035
F value			7.65				
P value			0.000				
Adjusted R ²			0.0811				

Table 7 Regression Analysis Results of Manufacturing Listed Companies in Shanghai Stock Exchange

Code	Non-Normalized Coefficient		Standard Coefficient		t	Sig.	Collinear Statistics	
	B	Standard Error	Trial version				Toleranc e	VIF
(constant)	0.07	0.023			2.969	0.003		
IC	-0.003	0.002	-0.138		-2.28	0.023	0.865	1.157
SIZE	-0.001	0.001	-0.059		-0.835	0.404	0.644	1.552
LEV	0.016	0.008	0.158		2.161	0.032	0.599	1.671
GROWTH	0.001	0.003	0.016		0.286	0.775	0.964	1.037
ROA	0.003	0.024	0.009		0.145	0.885	0.757	1.32
TOP10	-0.003	0.008	-0.02		-0.356	0.722	0.982	1.018
F value			12.44					
P value			0.000					
Adjusted R ²			0.0608					

It can be seen from Tables 6 and 7 above that the regression models of manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchange have passed the F test, and the model is significantly related as a whole. In the case of large sample data, the model R-squared is not optimal, but it is a normal phenomenon. All variables have tolerances greater than 0.5, VIFs are between 1 and 2, and the model does not have multiple collinearity issues. The correlation coefficient between internal control quality and earnings management of manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen Stock Exchange is -0.005, indicating a negative correlation between the two. The p-value corresponding to the t-value of -3.439 passed the significance test of 1%, indicating that the manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen Stock Exchange have the negative correlation between internal control and earnings management, confirming hypothesis 1. The correlation coefficient between internal control and earnings management of manufacturing listed companies in the Shanghai Stock Exchange is -0.003, corresponding to a t- value of -2.28, and the p- value corresponding to the t- value passed the 5% significance test. A negative coefficient also confirmed hypothesis 1.

The full sample regression analysis table 5, Shenzhen stock exchange regression analysis table 6 and Shanghai stock exchange regression analysis table 7 are integrated into table 8 for comparative analysis.

Table 8 Model Regression Analysis Results Comparison

Code	Full Sample Companies		Shenzhen Stock Exchange		Shanghai Stock Exchange	
	Regression Coefficients	t value	Regression Coefficients	t value	Regression coefficients	t value
(constant)	0.071	4.303	0.07	3.034	0.07	2.969
IC	-0.004	-4.199	-0.005	-3.439	-0.003	-2.28
SIZE	-0.001	-0.967	-0.001	-0.542	-0.001	-0.835
LEV	0.009	1.741	0.004	0.665	0.016	2.161
GROWTH	0.001	1.816	0.001	1.799	0.001	0.286
ROA	0.016	1.093	0.022	1.215	0.003	0.145
TOP10	0.005	1.075	0.01	1.45	-0.003	-0.356

F value	31.44	7.65	12.44
P value	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adjusted R ²	0.0795	0.0811	0.0608

Comparison of the corresponding results in the second row of Table 8, the analysis shows that the correlation coefficient between internal control and earnings management of listed companies in manufacturing industries are all significantly negative. The correlation coefficient between internal control and earnings management for the entire sample companies is -0.004, t-value is -4.199, 5% level is significant; the correlation coefficient between internal control and earnings management for the sample companies in Shenzhen stock exchange is -0.005, t-value is -3.439, 1% is significant; the correlation coefficient between the IC and EM for the sample companies in Shanghai stock exchange is -0.003, and the t-value is -2.28, which is significant at the 5% level. Through a comparative analysis of the correlation coefficient, t value, and significance level between Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchange, it is obvious that the negative correlation between internal control and earnings management of manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen stock exchange is more significant. Hypothesis 2 is confirmed and further illustrates the state policies of internal control regulations stated has been well implemented in manufacturing companies in the main board market, which has effectively played a role in regulating earnings management. The internal control normative guidelines have not yet been enforced in companies, which are in SMEB and GEM and the degree of EM of the companies in Shenzhen stock exchange is more significant than that in Shanghai stock market.

4.5 Robustness Test of the Model

There are many models for measuring earnings management. Different regression methods may obtain different results for the regression analysis. The modified JOHNS model is selected previously, and the extended Jones model proposed by Lu Jianqiao is re-selected to re-measure earnings management| DA |^[8]. The data re-regression analysis is done to verify the robustness of the model. The model is as follows:

$$\frac{TA_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = \beta_0 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \beta_1 \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t} - \Delta REC_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{PPE_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \beta_3 \frac{IA_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (6)$$

Among them, IA is intangible assets and other long-term assets.

Table 9 Robustness Test Regression Analysis Results

Code	Full sample Companies		Shenzhen Stock Exchange		Shanghai Stock Exchange	
	Regression Coefficients	t value	Regression Coefficients	t value	Regression Coefficients	t value
IC	-0.0022	-3.145	-0.0022	-2.453	-0.0021	-1.993
SIZE	-0.001	-1.48	-0.001	-1.569	0.000	-0.626
LEV	0.004	1.375	0.005	1.281	0.003	0.689
GROWTH	0.001	1.356	0.001	1.19	0.002	0.854
ROA	0.000	0.011	-0.003	-0.196	0.007	0.313
TOP10	0.003	0.929	0.002	0.378	0.005	0.909
F value	7.68		12.4		14.45	
P value	0.000		0.000		0.000	
Adjusted R ²	0.0814		0.0589		0.1257	

According to the regression analysis results in Table 9 above, the regression coefficients between the independent variable and the dependent variable of the entire sample of companies and manufacturing listed companies in the Shenzhen stock exchange are -0.0022, and the manufacturing listed companies in the Shanghai Stock Exchange is -0.0021. Combining the t value, we can know that internal control of the entire manufacturing listed companies including Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges are significantly negatively

correlated with earnings management. Hypothesis 1 is confirmed. A further comparison of the absolute value of the regression coefficients between Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges shows that the negative correlation of the manufacturing listed companies in Shenzhen stock exchange is more significant than in Shanghai stock exchange. Hypothesis 2 is therefore confirmed and it passes the robustness test.

5 Research Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

5.1 Research Conclusion

This research focuses on 2017 data with 884 listed manufacturing companies on the main board, SMEB and GEM of Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges to explore the impact of internal control on corporate earnings management and fill the research limitation of previous research which only focused on the main board and enrich the research area of earnings management, and verify the implementation effect of internal control guidelines(ICG) published by China Government on manufacturing listed companies.

The research conclusions and future research directions of this article include:

The internal control and earnings management of listed manufacturing companies are negatively correlated and have a significant relationship. The better the internal control, the lower the degree of earnings management. This shows that a comprehensive internal control system and well-implemented internal control measurements can restrict earnings management to a certain extent.

Compared with listed companies in Shanghai stock exchange, the negative correlation between internal control and earnings management of listed companies in Shenzhen stock exchange is more significant. This may be due to the fact that Shenzhen stock exchange includes not only the main board, but also SMEB and GEM listed companies. These companies of SMEB and GEM have relatively weak internal controls and have not been enforced internal control normative guidelines. They have more motivation to conduct earnings management. This also indicates that, Internal Control Normative Guidelines has a good implementation effect in the manufacturing listed companies in main board market.

Future research directions can divide earnings management into accrual and real earnings management, and compare and study the impact of the implementation of internal control regulations in Shenzhen and Shanghai Stock Exchange on the two types of earnings management.

5.2 Policy Suggestions

The conclusions of this study have important implications and policy suggestions: For the supervisory authorities, the "Basic Standards for Enterprise Internal Control" and "Guidelines for the Internal Control of Enterprises" issued by the state's multi-sector authorities are mandatory for companies listed on main board of Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges and the implementation effect is well done in the manufacturing listed companies. It is suggested that the supervisory authorities should further strengthen the internal control construction of the main board market, and include listed companies of SMEB and GEM in the scope of mandatory internal control information disclosure, continuously improve the overall internal control level of listed companies in China, and promote the healthy and orderly development of Chinese capital market.

For listed companies, the internal control environment is the foundation for the establishment and improvement of internal control system, and the company must increase the awareness of internal control information disclosure and risk control for all members, especially senior management. According to the actual situation of companies themselves, companies should set up internal control system suitable for companies themselves, and continuously modify and improve according to the company's development status, and build a multi-faceted, comprehensive, balanced and reasonable internal control system. At the same time, the implementation and supervision of internal control should be strengthened to ensure the consistent and effective implementation of internal control. According to the theory of information asymmetry and principal-agent theory, companies must weaken the motivation of earnings management from the source, such as improving the company's internal governance structure and equity structure, to prevent the emergence of "one dominant company" and "insider

control"; improve remuneration system, establish an effective incentive mechanism; rationally plan financial index, among others.

Advice to stakeholders is that, earnings management is common in the capital market, so stakeholders should not only pay attention to the financial status and operating results of the company and other financial index, but also pay attention to the disclosure of internal control information and other non-financial index so as to obtain a comprehensive information as possible for the right decision making.

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